

GENESIS AND SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Nizamova Shoira Isamiddinovna

Department of "Primary Education" of PERFECT University v. b. associate professor

E-mail: nizamova.shoira@bk.ru

Abstract

This article analyzes the genesis of management of educational institutions on the example of higher education. The experience of foreign countries in the management of higher education is studied on the example of the USA. The socio-economic development strategy is related to the globalization and integration taking place in the 21st century world, and the importance of education and science is covered in the article.

Key words

management, genesis, market requirements, SWOT analysis, benchmarking, image, price.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of development of the higher education system until 2030 serves as a part of economic and political reforms based on the principle of gradual and gradual development of building a new society in the country[1]. In order to expand the independence of higher education institutions, drastically reduce the state administrative management in their activities, and thereby to form state higher education institutions that train highly qualified personnel who can meet the demands of the changing labor market, granting financial independence gives the following additional powers to state higher education institutions. We all know that the development of education and science, ensuring the harmony of science and production, restructuring of production on the basis of science, timely implementation of scientific achievements and inventions in practice is the main factor in the development of society. Based on the study of the higher education system of developed countries in the world, the financial independence of higher education institutions determines the educational directions and the number of admissions for the training of specialists based on the market requirements based on the development of the country and the need for the necessary specialists. We

consider the genesis of the methods used in the management of universities in developed countries based on the management in the United States of America.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Ge-ne-zis (Yun. genesis - origin, emergence) means origin, history of emergence. Management has its own history of management methods and forms of education. I.O. Fomina, who conducted scientific research in the field of management, in his article entitled "Characteristics of the strategy for the development of higher education in the United States in modern conditions" defined the strategy of socio-economic development with the globalization and integration of the 21st century, in which science plays the main role and the process is carried out in developed countries. It is also reflected in the reforms, and scientific research institutes related to the field point out that priority is given to the implementation of the problem [2]. The USA has a unique experience in the management of educational institutions, which has been successfully combined with research activities in the higher education system engaged in projects related to the field. These studies show that there are different criteria in the management of educational institutions. Including: availability of public and private sector share of financing; the diversity of educational services in educational institutions (non-profit educational institutions created for the purpose of providing education and commercial ones created by the founders to receive financial benefits from educational activities); post-secondary two-year colleges and technical schools; universities that provide higher professional qualifications, academic and scientific degrees); research institutes and scientific centers.

Boston College professor and scholar Philip J., founder of Boston College's Center for the Study of International Higher Education. Altbach and Jamil Salmi, an international expert in the field of higher education, try to determine what drives the success of American research universities, identifying a number of figures and the factors that actively influence them [3].

The first factor group includes diversified funding sources. Budget funds are used for financial support of scientific research conducted in universities.

The second factor is the presence of a contingent of highly qualified employees, scientists, international and talented students and their motivation. In all specialized fields, the decision about how and what to study depends more on the content of the academic. At the beginning, the involvement of foreign specialists plays an important role in the development of advanced sectors of the US economy, brings economic, political and cultural benefits to the country. The arrival of teachers from other countries as labor emigrants contributes to the

increase of intellectual capital. Foreign teachers try to strengthen their position in new jobs. This is reflected in their commitment to research and mobility.

The third factor is the presence of a regulatory framework in the country that supports scientific research and activities, a high level of "internal" management mechanisms in universities, and a well-established investment policy in universities.

A system of additional incentives for university teaching staff is being introduced now. This, of course, has a significant impact on the quality of education, the increase in work efficiency, the work of professors and other employees on themselves, research and attitude to work, and the increase in responsibility.

METHODOLOGY AND METHODS

In the second half of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, retrospective and logical analysis methods were used to review the socio-economic conditions and characteristics of higher education institutions in the United States of America. Conclusions about the state of higher education in the USA and prospects for development were made based on the review of the content of official documentary sources and official statistical data and the author's interpretation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The leading research universities of the USA ensure dynamic development by reducing the dependence on economic instability, diversifying funding sources, concentrating talents in the teaching, scientific and student environment, ensuring academic mobility and a favorable management structure, and adequately respond to modern problems. The higher education system in the country has chosen the path of innovative development in modern conditions. For this, they have focused on strategic planning.

With the help of a strong strategy, management, university mission, goals and tasks for the future are developed, strategic priorities are formed, and mid- and long-term development programs of a promising university are determined. Determining the position of the university allows a comprehensive analysis of the university's position among competitors, including SWOT analysis, analysis of driving forces, internal analysis of the state of the organization, analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of the main competitors.

Fig. 1. Components of complex approach in university management.

Strategic management ensures the effectiveness of management activities of the higher educational institution. Three issues are important in strategic management:

- location;
- depends on what direction he chooses;
- how to start an activity in the organization.

These issues correspond to three main stages of strategic management: strategic analysis, strategic choice (or strategic planning) and strategy implementation[4].

The next issue that ensures the development of the American university is the well-established marketing education services. The potential of the university is determined by the existence of a high-potential competitive environment, the proper management of the university. In order to ensure high quality educational services, sustainable competitiveness, effective marketing formation and the existence of programs aimed at its implementation.

The competitiveness of the university increases in the following cases: the provided educational services meet market requirements and the consumer size of the consumer audience. Among these parameters, educational services can be singled out, the quality of educational services, the image of the university, the type of educational services, and the price of educational services.

The quality of S-educational services leads to an increase in the number of applicants for these Olympiads, preparatory courses, for evaluating student performance; the existence of a credit system for teaching, the involvement of practitioners in scientific teaching activities, readiness for national and international accreditation, the existence of a self-assessment and certification system at the university, strategic cooperation with leading foreign universities,

modern information technologies and material-technical base meet market requirements.

The image of the I-University is defined by an active marketing policy, advertising, IT programs, holding open days, cooperation with mass media, cooperation with state agencies, production companies, organization of meetings with business circles, holding international conferences. It can be seen that strategic management; operational management, institutional management, quality management, benchmarking, marketing research, integrated approach and human resource management.

N-price US universities tuition exchange programs, performance-based benefits and scholarships system consists of paid tuition, additional education services.

C-service is a rich infrastructure of education with university processes for example; development of publishing activities, expansion of new construction university buildings, organization of laboratory and practical training areas.

The next main tool of effective management is the benchmarking of the university's activities. At the moment, the most clearly defined concept of benchmarking can be defined as a continuous process of measurement and

comparing the work processes of one organization with related processes another organization to identify, learn and apply best practices [5].

The purpose of benchmarking is to familiarize the organization's management with external standards to help assess the quality and cost of internal processes and identify opportunities for improvement.

With benchmarking, universities are trying to answer the following;

- 1) how well do we do compared to others?
- 2) how successful do we want to be?
- 3) who will have the best success?
- 4) how did they achieve this?
- 5) How can we use their experience in our organization?
- 6) How can we be better than the best?

According to the trends in education in recent years, the growth of education financing and competition, the presence of ideas on how universities can improve their internal processes. The pursuit of efficiency is the rational management of entrepreneurship to further strengthen institutional management. Since the benchmarking method is based on statistics and research methodology, it is especially suitable for the university, and the practice covers all areas of activity.

Benchmarking helps overcome resistance to change, according to many university experts who have applied to this method.

Currently, the benchmarking method is widely used in America professional education associations (NACUBO - National Association of College and University Business Officers - and ACHE - The Association for Continuing Higher Education), selected universities (University of Chicago, public universities of Oregon, Pennsylvania, Utah, etc.), private consulting companies (Educational Benchmarking, The Benchmarking Exchange, etc. [6]). The European Center for Strategic Management of Universities is well known in Europe (ESMU, Belgium), where the "Benchmarking" program has been successfully implemented for several years. This program introduced all participating universities to the possibility of management analysis and improvement.

The European Network for Quality Assurance in Higher Education ENQA developed seven principles for this [7]:

1. Educational quality assessment standards.
2. Monitoring and periodic evaluation.
3. Assessment of students' knowledge level.
4. Ensuring the quality of professors and teachers.
5. Learning resources and student support.
6. Monitoring the operation of information systems.
7. Establishment of cooperation with mass media.

The above management principles and approaches of modern management implemented in universities allow to improve university activity, effective development, and at the same time increase its competitiveness in the market of educational services. The development of the higher education system in foreign developed countries is based on these two features of central management and the diversification of the training of specialists in higher education institutions based on the requirements of market relations [8].

CONCLUSION

Studying the experience of Higher Education Management in advanced mamalakats on the example of the United States helps to find a specific way to choose a management strategy and effectively modernize higher education in its organization.

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